

FEATURES OF PREPARATION OF RUNNERS FOR MIDDLE AND LONG DISTANCES, CADETS STUDYING IN ACADEMIES OF THE MIA OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation.

The article presents a theoretical substantiation of the need to improve individual training, the role of running training in anaerobic mode, the use of an individual approach in the training of athletes from among cadets and trainees participating in athletics competitions. An approach to the development of a methodology for improving individual running technique based on identifying the specific capabilities of an athlete is outlined.

Key words: running, physical fitness, physical abilities, medium and long distances, running technique.

The Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan pays a lot of attention to improving the physical fitness of cadets and students, as well as the moral and volitional qualities of future officers of the Internal Affairs Ministry. One of the leading areas of the Department of Combat and Physical Training is the improvement of sportsmanship, since sport is an integral part of the physical education of future officers. Training in sports helps to form skills related to quick orientation in different situations, timely decision making and many other things. In addition, it should not be forgotten that the cadets of power structures universities are a reserve for sports of the highest achievements. Middle- and long-distance running are popular in our country.

So, running is one of the main components of service-applied sports and is one of the control exercises on endurance. Employees, cadets and listeners of the Academy of the MIA Uzbekistan take part in track and field cross-country competitions, for example: "Men ʻolib, Vatan qalkoni, Yangi nafas, Tashkent International Marathon", etc., where cadet athletes compete at different distances (3,5, 10 km).

Recently, there have been quite a lot of scientific works and studies covering the issues of sports physiology, sports medicine, sports psychology, including the study of specific characteristics of sports training with the use of experience in the training process of athletes. These studies describe the features of running technique, various methods of preparation for competitions, the importance of tactics in middle and long distance running and other components that allow to achieve decent results in this sport.

Analysis of the literature showed that the issues affecting the specifics of the training of middle and long distance runners during training in departmental educational organizations remain unaddressed until now. During the study of scientific literature and relying on the main moments of the training process and activity of middle and long distance runners it was concluded that the most important and basic components of a good result in this kind of athletics is technical and tactical training, as well as the methodology of training runners

including two main directions: improving running technique and increasing the functional capabilities of the cadets body.

The study of training approaches in departmental universities, the theory and methodology of physical education contributed to the definition of the following modern trends:

1. the emphasis of the training process should coincide with the natural acceleration in the development of individual elements of motor skills of the cadet athlete.
2. training should be carried out depending on the type of moral and psychological features of cadet-athletes.

It is important to note that athletes who are trained at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Uzbekistan. in contrast to students of other civilian universities, devote their time both to service and to the educational process. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the energy expenditures in the performance of service activities: cleaning the territory, duty in the 24-hour guards, training practice and internships at the place of future service. All these activities have a strong impact on the body of cadets and trainees in terms of physical and emotional load, as well as reduce the time baggage of the athlete.

During the study of methodological recommendations related to the training of middle and long distance runners, it was noted that the inborn and acquired individual abilities and features of cadets, as well as their level of special training, psychological development and the specifics of training and service activity are often not taken into account. All of these criteria have a negative impact on the training of middle and long distance runners. The way to success and achievement of positive results in any sport, as well as in athletics, lies through the performance of a repeated number of different exercises, trainings. To achieve high results in middle and long distance running it is necessary to devote a lot of time to daily training throughout the school year.

It should be taken into account that such sports training should be reasonably planned, to ensure the necessary load and recovery of the body. Taking into account the above features of training at the Academy of the MIA Uzbekistan it is necessary to use an individual approach to train athletes from among cadets and trainees participating in competitions in athletics and service multiathlon.

In this case, training at all stages of development of athletes' sports form during the period of study at the university should be strictly cyclic in nature. Thus, each cycle, represents another stage in the preparation of the athlete, in which the amount of load is mastered, which is physiologically justified precisely for him and for a particular stage of development of his level of training. Poor planning in the preparation of runners, and especially the relatively low intensity of the training process or the uneven distribution of the competitive load, are deficiencies that some coaches make. As a result, this kind of incompetence prevents cadet athletes from achieving high results.

Currently, there are many methods for training athletes to achieve high performance in competitive running, including, but not limited to: high-volume aerobic loads; intense stretches on the treadmill; and tempo cross-country runs. However, which method for the development of professionalism and speed endurance is the most appropriate for the athlete is determined by the coach. As for the peculiarities of the method of running for a particular distance, then, for example, running for medium and long distances refers to the zone of work of "submaximal power". That is, one of the indicators that characterize this work is the "oxygen debt", which increases during competitive running and reaches a significant value by

the end of the distance, and the most important factors in the preparedness of runners include the physical capabilities of the athlete - the level of development of basic motor qualities such as: speed, flexibility, strength, endurance largely depends and the improvement of technical and tactical preparedness of the athlete.

Thus, increasing the level of physical fitness is a fundamental task of athletic training. In short- and long-distance running, endurance is important, which is the body's ability to resist fatigue. And the leading special quality is the speed endurance, that is, the ability to maintain the pace over the entire distance of running. To develop speed endurance among cadets specializing in running, the training process should be structured so that the tasks of developing general and then speed endurance are systematically solved. It has been repeatedly expressed in the special literature on athletics that it is possible to increase special endurance by increasing the average intensity of training, that is, by applying different training loads and increasing their variability. In addition, the development of speed qualities is always promoted by sports games, which require the athlete to have special endurance when performing short and long jerks at maximum speed.

Anaerobic running training plays an important role in the athlete's training. It is also necessary to simulate the mode of competitive running, in particular, when the final part of the distance takes place with a strong so-called "acidification" of the body. Also the improvement of technical and tactical skills of the athlete should be carried out at a speed close to the competitive one. In this regard, the volume of anaerobic running in the overall structure of cadet training should be significant. In fact, the training strategy is to gradually increase the share of special training as the cadet or trainee's sportsmanship grows. It should be concluded that the high performance of runners of the Academy of the MIA Uzbekistan can be achieved by improving individual sports skills and eliminating deficiencies in the training of cadets - athletes. And the growing popularity of athletics stimulates the search for new methods of training athletes. The use of new and effective methods of training provides a steady increase in sports results in running for medium and long distances.

The methodology of development of functional capabilities of cadet-athletes includes various approaches, and in technical training the priorities of classical school are noted. To achieve high sports results in the preparation of cadets it seems necessary to increase the technical preparedness of middle and long distance runners by searching for new effective and high-quality methods. In addition, to improve the individual technique of running of a particular athlete, it is of great importance to determine its physiological characteristics, which is important to determine the pedagogical methodology, which should have an effective impact on the essence of the training process.

Conclusions. Using an individual approach in the preparation of athletes from among cadets and trainees participating in competitions in athletics, improving individual technique of running based on the identification of specific capabilities of the athlete, as well as the use of the basic components of athletics training can achieve positive results in running for medium and long distances.

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